

Project information

Project full title	LEAPS pilot to foster open innovation for accelerator-based light sources in Europe
Project acronym	LEAPS-INNOV
Grant agreement no.	101004728
Instrument	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Duration	01/04/2021 – 31/09/2025
Website	www.leaps-innov.eu

Deliverable information

Deliverable no.	1.7
Deliverable title	Recommendations of RI-INNOV Coordination Group
Deliverable responsible	DESY
Related Work-Package/Task	WP1: Task
Type (e.g. Report; other)	Report
Author(s)	E. Plönjes, A. Thiess, U. Lächele, M. Vretenar
Dissemination level	Public
Document Version	1
Date	30.01.2025
Download page	

Document information

Version no.	Date	Author(s)	Comment
1	12.12. 2024	E. Plönjes	
2	16.12. 2024	A. Thiess	
3	20.01. 2024	M. Vretenar	
4	28.01. 2024	E. Plönjes	
5	29.01.2024	U. Lächele	
6	30.1.2024	E. Plönjes	

Recommendations of RI-INNOV Coordination Group

1. Summary

A RI Co-Innovation Platform has been set up and implemented by the “Advanced Communities” of RIs addressed in the Horizon 2020 call INFRAINNNOV-04-2020. It is coordinated by an RI Open Innovation Coordination Group (RI-INNOV CG). The group has performed joint support actions to foster the innovation potential in European RIs. The general goals of the coordination group have been cooperation on innovation related actions, exchange of information and jointly strengthening collaboration with industry.

The regular in-depth exchange between the projects I.FAST, AIDAInnova and LEAPS-INNOV has led to joint initiatives and workshops to present the actions and outcomes regularly throughout the project duration of the three projects. Additionally, feedback on these actions has been provided jointly to EC. A final recommendation of the coordination group is to keep the lively exchange between the communities active beyond the project duration through the LEAPS, TIARA and AIDA communities.

2. Overview of the Exchange Platform

- **Objectives:** The “Advanced Communities” of RIs addressed in the call INFRAINNNOV-04-2020 agreed to implement an RI Co-Innovation Platform. In order to exploit synergies, coordinate activities, and share results among the selected innovation pilots (light source technologies, accelerator technologies, and detector technologies for accelerators) the coordination group has addressed the following proposed objectives:

(i) to define a common approach for the scientific areas that are at the boundaries between the competences of the different communities,

(ii) to exchange information on the advancement and results of the respective projects,

(iii) to identify areas of cooperation and, where appropriate, to launch common initiatives in the form of workshops, studies, joint position papers, etc. Possible areas of cooperation cover technology transfer, models and schemes for cooperation with industry, standardisation of equipment, training, etc.

The “RI Innovation Knowledge and Technology Transfer Network” (RI-INNOV KTT network) exchanges on knowledge and technology transfer models exploited by the various innovation pilots.

- **Structure and Participants:**

To facilitate an effective exchange, an RI Open Innovation Coordination Group (RI-INNOV CG) and a RI-INNOV KTT network have been formed:

- RI-INNOV CG (Coordination group):

The RI-INNOV-CG is coordinated by the three project coordinators. Its members are the scientific coordinator and her/his deputy and one other representative. At its first meeting, the group has nominated a chair being in charge of organising the meetings. The chair is rotated on a regular basis between the communities.

Additional project members such as the WP leaders of the “industry-relation” work packages, organisers of the BSBF activities, or the ATTRACT coordinator have been invited on need.

- RI-INNOV KTT network:

A joint “RI Innovation Knowledge and Technology Transfer (KTT) Network” of knowledge- and technology transfer experts from partners of the successful projects of INFRAINNOV-04-2020 has been part of the RI Co-Innovation Platform. It is managed on work package level, i.e. in LEAPS-INNOV by WP8.

- **Implementation:**

- RI-INNOV CG

At the beginning of the projects, the members have signed a memorandum of understanding (MoC, see appendix), defined joint activities and clarified possible collaboration with the other projects, e.g. ATTRACT (INFRAINNOV-03-2020). The RI-INNOV CG meets at least twice a year, as agreed in the MoU.

Regular exchange every 2-3 months of the coordination group has been realized throughout the project duration. The complete list of 21 meetings from October 2019 to December 2024 is available at <https://indico.cern.ch/category/16380/>, with access to the agenda and accompanying material for each meeting.

- RI-INNOV KTT network

The aim is to exchange experience and best practice on collaboration with industry and support the RI-INNOV CG in implementing joint activities in field of KT/TT. Dedicated meetings at least once a year and exchange at appropriate events such as the biennial Big Science Business Forum (BSBF) have regularly been organized throughout the duration of the projects.

3. Key Achievements and Impact

- **Scientific, Technological and Innovation Actions of RI-INNOV Coordination Group:**
The INFRA-INNOV pilots coordination group has stimulated exchange on innovation amongst the advanced communities of research infrastructures.
 - Presentation of the planned and ongoing actions and outcomes of all pilots at the respective annual meetings in 2022 and 2023.
 - Several online workshops on Intellectual Property Rights management, organized by LEAPS-INNOV, webinar open to AIDA and iFAST, invitation circulated
 - Presentations of actions and outcomes at BSBF 2022, Granada and BSBF2024, Trieste
 - Common presentation for the TIPP2023 Conference, Cape Town, South Africa, Sept 4-8, 2023: P. Giacomelli presentation on behalf of INFRA-INNOV at the Knowledge & Technology Transfer session at the TIPP23 conference: <https://indico.tlabs.ac.za/event/112/overview>. Title “Co-developments with industries within large EU funded infrastructural projects
 - Presentation at 85th ESFRI Forum, Tenerife, Spain (José Manuel Pérez, TIARA), Sept 28-29, 2023
 - Joint Industry Workshop on “Cryogenics in Big Science”, April 16-17, 2024
 - Common booth and presentations of pilot outcomes at BSBF 2024, Trieste, Italy, Oct. 1-4, 2024

Impressions from BSBF 2024

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004728

- INFRA-INNOV COORDINATION – DG/RTD A4, Brussels July 13, 2023
- Innovation Pilots Workshop with ATTRACT, Oct 14, 2024
- **Scientific, Technological and Innovation Actions of KTT Network:**
 - Meet-up in person at BSBF 2022 on LEAPS booth for those there from ICO and procurement side, Oct. 5, 2022
 - LEAPS-INNOV, I.FAST and AIDAInnova participated in “BIGINN Know and Tech Transfer workshop” at HZB Berlin, March 9, 2023

Impressions from BIGINN Know and Tech Transfer workshop

HZB, Berlin 2023

- AIDAInnova Advanced Mechanics Workshop in Valencia, April 27, 2023

- Joint LEAPS ICO meeting in Lund with participation of AIDAInnova and I.FAST, May30 – June 1, 2023

Group Photo, Lund 2023

- Harwell Science Campus, Big Science event with suppliers, Nov. 3, 2023
- ALBA Synchrotron, Industry opportunities in light sources infrastructures, Dec. 1, 2023
- Joint activities at BSBF 2024 showcasing project results, Oct 1-4, 2024
- Anticipate combined meeting LEAPS-INNOV, RITRAIN+. RITIFI, AIDAInnova and I.FAST in spring 2025

- **Impact:**

The joint actions of the RI Co-Innovation Platform have led to significantly improved visibility of the innovation pilots in the RI communities and in the industrial landscape. In-depth presentation of the developed technologies and innovation actions and exchange with industry at a number of events has raised awareness of the opportunities at the involved RIs both, for industry as well as for the involved RIs themselves. This cooperation is now leading to new joint projects and activities.

A rigorous exchange on technologies at the border of the involved fields as well as innovation aspects has benefited the involved scientists and is also leading to combined actions on bringing these technologies forward for all communities. The strategic exchange between the accelerator, detector and lightsource communities benefits the respective roadmapping processes for FP10 as well as lessons learned on how to approach an effective exchange with industry. Finally, structured exchange with the European Commission benefits both, the RI communities as well as EC, in efficiently assessing the RI communities' needs.

4. Lessons Learned and Recommendations

- **Lessons learned**

Exchange of the organizational bodies (LEAPS, TIARA, AIDA), joint actions among the communities, towards industry and a joint conversation with EC has already resulted in common activities, strategic exchange in view of FP10 and will be most fruitful long-term. It will improve the conversation between scientists of the involved RI communities as well as identify joint opportunities for technology development, user engagement and working with industry as well as enable discussions about synergies and the identification and definition of the necessary steps for their implementation.

The RI Platform requires a sustainable organization between the communities and voluntary involved in future actions from all three communities. An organization team for the exchange between the communities is required long-term and needs to be based within the consortia of the respective communities, i.e. LEAPS, TIARA and AIDA. Communities could take turn yearly to organize and chair the platform.

- **Recommendations**

The RI-INNOV coordination group recommends to keep the RI Platform active beyond the duration of the innovation pilots which will end in September 2025. An active RI platform allows for a better and faster exchange and therefore a higher strategic impact within and beyond their respective communities. However, a meaningful long-term interaction requires funding for joint actions and travel for meetings.

Joint technology developments for technologies relevant for all communities as well as innovation actions can benefit all communities equally. At the same time it also has to be recognized that significant differences exist, for example in many technology areas needed for RI operation (e.g. optics and user instruments for LEAPS), but also aspects such as transnational access and user involvement. Identifying common and differing areas of interest improves shaping of the respective profiles and targeting the most appropriate funding options.

Both, the involved research and technology development communities as well as policy makers like the EC, can benefit from such a structured exchange platform which could also be expanded towards additional RI communities in the future.

The platform's sustainability will most certainly be enhanced by (limited) support from EC. Based on the common experience of the pilot communities, models for long-term support for key technological areas of European Research Infrastructures can and should be identified and developed.

5. Appendix

INFRA-INNOV MoC

On 3 December 2021, the Memorandum of Cooperation between the 3 projects INFRA-INNOV (LEAPS-INNOV, AIDA-INNOVA and I-FAST) has been signed.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101004728

INFRAINNOV-04 MoC

**INFRAINNOV-04-2020
Memorandum of Cooperation
("MoC")**

BETWEEN: the members of the consortium implementing the Advancement and Innovation for Detectors and Accelerators Project ("AIDAInnova"),

AND: the members of the consortium implementing the Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology Project ("I.FAST"),

AND: the members of the consortium implementing the League of European Accelerator based-Photon Sources Innovation Project ("LEAPS-INNOV"),

Hereinafter collectively referred to as the "Projects" and individually as a "Project", in each case represented by the Project Coordinator for the purposes of the signature of this MoC.

WHEREAS:

In 2019, the European Commission (the "Funding Authority") opened a call for proposals under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme to foster the innovation potential of research infrastructures by making industry more aware of the opportunities offered by research infrastructures to improve their products; and to encourage research infrastructures to work with industry on the development of advanced technologies to raise their technological level and competitiveness ("INFRAINNOV-04-2020");

The Projects were selected for funding by the Funding Authority under INFRAINNOV-04-2020;

AIDAInnova advances the European detector development infrastructures through fostering an intensified co-innovation, following on from the success of the previous EU-funded initiatives AIDA and AIDA-2020;

I.FAST enhances innovation in and from accelerator-based research infrastructures, following on from the success of the previous EU-funded initiative, ARIES;

LEAPS-INNOV fosters open innovation for accelerator-based light sources in Europe, following on from the success of the previous EU-funded initiative, CALIPSOplus;

The Projects recognise that coordination and collaboration between them will enhance their innovation strategy and facilitate an exchange of ideas, while avoiding a duplication of work on critical common challenges;

**HAVING IDENTIFIED THE POTENTIAL FOR SYNERGIES BETWEEN THEM,
THE PROJECTS HEREBY AGREE AS FOLLOWS:**

1. Purpose

1.1 This MoC establishes the framework for collaboration between the Projects.

Page 1 of 4

INFRAINNOV-04 MoC

- 1.2 Each of the Projects shall participate in the collaborative activities contemplated by this MoC subject to the availability of resources and on a reasonable efforts basis, without any warranty or guarantee as to results or otherwise.
- 1.3 This MoC is not legally binding, but the Projects recognise that the success of the collaborative activities will depend on the adherence to the MoC provisions.

2. Collaborative activities

The Projects will share information concerning their activities, including their approaches, methodologies and experience, subject to any contrary pre-existing confidentiality and intellectual property obligations.

3. Organisation

The organisational structure of the collaboration under this MoC shall comprise the following bodies:

- An RI-Open Innovation Coordination Group (“the Coordination Group”) to perform joint support actions to foster innovation potential in the Projects; and
- An RI-Innovation Knowledge and Technology Transfer Network (the “KTT Network”) to exchange experience and best practise on collaboration with industry and support the Coordination Group in implementing joint activities.

4. Mandate of the Coordination Group

- 4.1 The Coordination Group shall consist of the Project Coordinators, their deputies and one further member from each Project consortium, as well as the chair of the KTT Network.
- 4.2 The Coordination Group shall meet at least twice per year, either in person or by teleconference.
- 4.3 At its first meeting, the Coordination Group will appoint a chair from among its members and establish its own operational procedures. The chair shall be responsible for the organisation of meetings and the preparation of the associated agenda.
- 4.4 The Coordination Group has the following objectives:
 - defining a common strategy for scientific areas which are at the boundaries between the competencies of the Projects;
 - identifying areas of cooperation and the potential launch of common initiatives in the form of workshops, studies and documentation;
 - strengthening collaboration with industry, to foster the innovation potential of the Projects; and
 - exchanging information internally on the follow-up of the Projects and any future initiatives launched.

5. Mandate of the KTT Network

- 5.1 The KTT Network shall consist of the knowledge (“KT”) and technology transfer (“TT”) experts of the Project consortium members.
- 5.2 The KTT Network shall meet twice per year, either in person or by teleconference.

INFRAINNOV-04 MoC

5.3 At its first meeting, the KTT Network will appoint a chair from among its members and shall establish its own operational procedures. The chair shall be responsible for the organisation of meetings and preparation of the associated agenda.

5.4 The KTT Network has the following objectives:

- exchanging knowledge and experience relating to collaboration with industry;
- discussing common strategies of communication with industry, standardisation and training, to manage interfaces and overlaps; and
- supporting the Coordination Group in the implementation of joint activities in the fields of KTT.

6. Liability

Except as expressly provided in this MoC, the Projects shall have no liability in connection with their participation in this collaboration.

7. Confidentiality

The Projects agree to execute this MoC in a spirit of openness. However, where, exceptionally, confidentiality is required, the confidentiality provisions stipulated in the respective consortium agreements for each Project shall apply. For the avoidance of doubt, the Projects shall obtain the consent of a disclosing Project prior to disclosing confidential information to a third party.

8. Duration

This MoC shall remain in force until the conclusion of the Projects.

9. Amendments

This MoC may be amended by written agreement of the Projects.

The Projects have caused their duly authorised Project Coordinators to sign three originals of this MoC on behalf of each Project's consortium members.

For the members of the AIDAInnova
Consortium

Felix Sefkow, DESY

For the members of the
L.FAST Consortium

Maurizio Vretenar, CERN

INFRAINNOV-04 MoC

For the members of the
LEAPS-INNOV Consortium

Prof. Dr. Dr. Helmut Dosch
Chairman of the DESY Board of Directors

Prof. Dr. Edgar Weckert
Director in charge of Photon Science

On: **03. Dez. 2021** 2021

Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY
Ein Forschungszentrum der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft
Notkestraße 85 | 22607 Hamburg | Tel. 0410 6050-0

